

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI TRANSPORT VAZIRLIGI
TOSHKENT DAVLAT TRANSPORT UNIVERSITETI**

**“TURKIY DAVLATLARNING O‘ZARO MANFAATLI
INTEGRATSIYASI – BARQAROR TARAQQIYOT
KAFOLATI”**

II xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya

MATERIALLARI TO‘PLAMI

Toshkent, 2025-yil 2-3-may

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UDK:

**“Turkiy davlatlarning o‘zaro manfaatli integratsiyasi – barqaror taraqqiyot
kafolati” II xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya to‘plami**

“Turkiy davlatlarning o‘zaro manfaatli integratsiyasi – barqaror taraqqiyot kafolati” II xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya to‘plamida jami 94 ta ilmiy maqola kiritilgan bo‘lib, mazkur maqolalar Turkiy davlatlar o‘rtasidagi iqtisod, siyosat, madaniyat, turizm sohalaridagi hamkorlik va imkoniyatlar, Barqaror kelajak uchun suv resurslarini boshqarishda iqlim o‘zgarishining roli, o‘rta asr Markaziy Osiyo allomalari ilmiy merosining uchinchi renessans poydevorini barpo etishdagi ahamiyati, Turkiy davlatlarda transport, muxandislik kommunikatsiyalari, energetika, logistika, turizm sohalaridagi integratsiya jarayonlari, Turkiy davlatlar o‘rtasidagi raqamli transformatsiya, fan, ta‘lim va innovatsion rivojlanish istiqbollari kabi yo‘nalishlarni ilmiy jihatdan ochib berilishiga qaratilgan. To‘plamda o‘zbek, rus, ozarbayjon, ingliz tillarida tayyorlangan maqolalar mavjud. Ushbu konferensiya to‘plamidan transport, iqtisodiyot, falsafa, pedagogika va tarix yo‘nalishidagi tadqiqotchilar keng foydalanishi mumkin.

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CENTRAL ASIA-EU COOPERATION: PROSPECTS AND CHALLENGES

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Annotation: Cooperation between the European Union and the Central Asian region has reached a new level. For the first time, a summit was held with the participation of the heads of state of the European Union and Central Asian states, during which the parties agreed to cooperate within the framework of a strategic partnership. Thus, the European Union decided to further develop relations with the region. This article will reveal the historical foundations of such closeness, the agreements reached within the framework of the Summit, the geopolitical prospects of cooperation between the regions and its significance for regional stability, and the new challenges for the region.

Keywords: Central Asia, European Union, cooperation, Summit, stability, green energy, global processes, confrontation, challenge, perspective, S5+1 format, integration, interest.

Annotatsiya: Yevropa Ittifoqi va Markaziy Osiyo mintaqalari o'rtasidagi hamkorlik yangi bosqichga chiqdi. Ilk bor Yevropa Ittifoqi va Markaziy Osiyo davlat rahbarlari ishtirokida sammit bo'lib o'tib unda tomonlar strategik sheriklik doirasida hamkorlik qilishga kelishib oldilar. Shu tariqa Yevropa Ittifoqi mintaqa bilan yanada yaqinlashishga bel bog'ladi. Ushbu maqolada bunday yaqinlikning tarixiy asoslari, Sammit doirasidagi kelishuvlar, mintaqalar o'rtasidagi hamkorlikning geosiyosiy istiqbollari va uning mintaqa barqarorligi uchun ahamiyati, mintaqa uchun yangi chaqiriqlar ularning mohiyati ochib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Markaziy Osiyo, Yevropa Ittifoqi, hamkorlik, Sammit, barqarorlik, yashil energetika, global jarayonlar, konfrontatsiya, chaqiriq, istiqbol, S5+1 formati, integratsiya, manfaat

Аннотация: Сотрудничество между Европейским Союзом и регионами Центральной Азии вышло на новый уровень. Впервые состоялся саммит с участием глав государств Евросоюза и Центральной Азии, на котором стороны договорились о сотрудничестве в рамках стратегического партнерства. Таким образом, Европейский Союз принял решение о дальнейшем развитии отношений с регионом. В статье будут рассмотрены исторические основы такой близости, достигнутые в рамках Саммита соглашения, геополитические перспективы сотрудничества между регионами и его значение для региональной стабильности, а также новые вызовы, стоящие перед регионом.

Ключевые слова: Центральная Азия, Европейский Союз, сотрудничество, Саммит, стабильность, зеленая энергетика, мировые процессы, конфронтация, вызов, перспектива, формат S5+1, интеграция, интерес.

Today, Central Asia is increasingly emerging as an independent and integrated pole of global processes. In any case, the leading geopolitical forces, the collective West, are creating an opportunity for this. Based on this, the C5+ format, which began with the initiative of Japan [1] and the United States[2] , has become popular, and today cooperation relations in this format have been formed with 8 actors [3].

An important feature of this format is that countries that have the status of geopolitical driving forces have begun to approach the countries of Central Asia as an integrated region. Its importance for Central Asia is a great opportunity to increase its political position and economic potential as an important platform for the region's dialogue with major powers.

The EU has a unique status within the framework of cooperation in the C5+1 format.

This is primarily because the EU is attractive as an integrated entity that can become a benchmark for our region, but at the same time, it is also important as an influential partner that the region invests in. About 40% of direct investments in the region are made by the EU.

Historical foundations of cooperation

After the countries of the region gained independence, the European Union began to establish cooperation with the countries of Central Asia. At that time, the priority aspects of cooperation were to support the implementation of economic, political and legal reforms during

the transition period. At the beginning of the new century, the European Union offered the countries of Central Asia more cooperation opportunities. In 2001, a new cooperation program for the region, “Renewing the European Union's Policy towards Central Asia”, was adopted in Europe. This program identified Central Asia as a key strategic partner of the EU. In 2002, the European Union developed new mechanisms to assist the countries of Central Asia in democratic and economic reforms. Much attention was paid to cooperation with the region in large infrastructure projects and energy resource management. In 2007, the European Union adopted a Central Asia Strategy. An important feature of it was the goals of strengthening bilateral relations with the countries of the region. In 2015, the European Union developed a strategy for the countries of Central Asia called “Central Asia - the European Union: Stability, Growth and Rapprochement”. This strategy includes increasing security, trade and investment, protecting human rights and supporting democratic reforms. In 2019, the European Union revised the Central Asia Strategy and set new goals and directions. The main emphasis was placed on further deepening cooperation between the European Union and the countries of Central Asia, and most importantly, developing multilateral cooperation.

C5+1 format

It should be recognized that the new “5+1” format of multilateral cooperation between the countries of Central Asia is an effective mechanism for regular dialogue between the countries of Central Asia and their foreign partners in order to develop ties, which, in turn, serves regional stability, economic and inclusive development. At the same time, the formation of new formats and areas of dialogue between the region and foreign partner states increases the geopolitical and economic importance of Central Asia. On the one hand, the “5+1” format is considered a convenient diplomatic platform for cooperation, on the other hand, according to the theory of “balancing regionalization”, it is an informal tool for implementing foreign policy through multilateral forms of cooperation and dialogue and balancing the influence of external forces. From this point of view, in the current geopolitical situation and conditions, it is extremely important for the Central Asian states to support multilateral and balanced cooperation with foreign partners. In addition, deepening regional cooperation is an effective factor in increasing the importance of Central Asia and resolving various issues in the interests of the region.

If we analyze the importance of multilateral cooperation or bilateral cooperation for the region, V. Komelova’s views on this are noteworthy. In her opinion, both formats are important. Bilateral relations allow us to resolve more sensitive issues and discuss behind-the-scenes issues. It is easier to reach agreements in bilateral formats. Therefore, they will always be relevant. Expanded collective formats, such as the C5+ format, allow us to determine the general rules of the game. For the Central Asian states themselves, they will allow them to better understand each other, develop common positions and adequately assess their resources[4].

EU-CA Samarkand Summit

As is known, the first Summit between the heads of state of the EU and Central Asia was held in Samarkand on April 4-5 of this year. The summit brought cooperation between the two regions to a new level.

Before the summit, the head of the host state, Sh. Mirziyoyev, gave an interview to EuroNews and spoke about expectations from the upcoming Summit and Uzbekistan's initiatives. He also made a speech during the summit and put forward important proposals. It was emphasized that it is the openness of Central Asia and its readiness for mutually beneficial cooperation with all partners that have become a condition for ensuring the security and

prosperity of the region. The countries of Central Asia have extensive positive experience in conducting geological exploration work with leading European companies and organizing high-tech production facilities for the development of strategic raw materials deposits and their deep processing. “We are in favor of deepening mutually beneficial cooperation with the European Union in this direction,” said Shavkat Mirziyoyev[5] . “The lack of effective transport corridors for the delivery of these products, as well as finished industrial and agricultural goods to European markets, is the main obstacle in this,” he said. “It is necessary to develop coordinated measures and favorable conditions for business to expand and supply the Trans-Caspian transport corridor with cargo. I am confident that these tasks fully correspond to the goals of the pan-European program “Global Gateway”. “In this regard, we propose to convene a meeting of transport ministers of countries located along this route under the auspices of the European Union to develop agreed approaches,” the head of Uzbekistan said [5]. “Uzbekistan fully supports the international project to supply electricity from the Central Asian region to Europe. On the eve of the summit, we ratified the relevant agreement on the implementation of this project,” the head of state said [5]. He noted that by 2030, Uzbekistan plans to increase the share of renewable energy in the country’s energy balance to 54 percent and launch 24 thousand MW of “green” capacity. “The establishment of the “Central Asia - European Union” partnership on “clean” energy can create an important platform for our cooperation. We also propose to establish a working group at the level of heads of related ministries to finance the development of “carbon credits” projects and develop their market. “We will present the concept of the region’s “Green” development during the upcoming Climate Forum,” he said [5].

At the summit, agreements were signed on the EU’s investment in the region of \$12 billion, the development of green energy, that is, the establishment of energy supplies to Europe through renewable energy sources, cooperation in the extraction of rare metals in the region, and the implementation of the Middle Corridor (Moscow-Caspian Sea-Trans-Caspian countries-Black Sea-Europe) project.

The leaders of the Central Asian countries and the European Union adopted a joint declaration elevating the parties’ relations to the level of strategic partnership. The document is aimed at developing trade, transport, energy, digital communications, and water resources management.

According to the declaration, relations between the parties have been elevated to the level of strategic partnership. The leaders agreed to cooperate for peace, security and democracy, while respecting international law and the UN Charter, including the territorial integrity of all states.

The Central Asian states and the European Union also agreed to continue cooperation to prevent the circumvention of sanctions.

The European Union welcomed the intensification of regional cooperation through regular consultative meetings of the Central Asian leaders and expressed its readiness to support future efforts towards regional integration.

Geopolitical analysis of the summit

If we analyze the summit from a geopolitical point of view, the EU was organized against the backdrop of an adequate response to the US president’s tariff “war”. The EU thereby tried to demonstrate to the US that it can act as an independent entity and that it also has its own capabilities. In addition, it began to demonstrate an adequate response to the recent US claims regarding rare metals. At the same time, it is seeking to further weaken Russia’s weakening influence in the region, thereby striking at Russian interests. It is no secret that continuing

cooperation is aimed precisely at Russia in order to prevent circumvention of the imposed sanctions. Or the “Middle Corridor” project, which bypasses Russia, is also contrary to Russian interests. Agreements related to the development of raw materials in the region are contrary to Chinese interests. Whether the “Middle Corridor” will be coordinated with China’s “One Belt, One Road” project or will be an alternative to it is still under question. Turkey, which has been developing cooperation with the region in the Turkic World format in recent times, is also concerned about the EU’s rapprochement with our region. The convergence of the EU and the EU’s approaches to the issue of Northern Cyprus worries the Turkish government. It is clear that this Summit is like a “horse whipping” before a new “big game” for the region. The reason is that the above global players will begin to move the next piece on the EU “chess field”. The complexity of the issue means that the leading powers do not want to easily give up their sphere of influence to the EU, which has a decisive position in the global geopolitical space. The movement of pieces by players on the regional chessboard is both an opportunity and a challenge for the region itself.

The superiority of the EU

It should be noted that the EU has not only new directions for increasing investment activity in the region, but also its own competitive advantages, unlike other countries. The EU is seen as a country that has achieved a strong technological leap thanks to innovation and human capital.

In addition, the EU can be seen as an economic and political balance in relations between the Central Asian countries and the Russian Federation and China.

Unlike other actors, the EU has always been more interested in developing regional cooperation between the countries of Central Asia, in order to jointly solve many internal problems, from ecology to water resources, along with establishing bilateral relations.

Central Asia is being perceived by the world community as an integral region. It is becoming increasingly clear that this will be an additional argument in favor of the regional integration of the five countries and will stimulate new dynamics in this process[6] .

The European Union’s strategy for Central Asia has a single goal: to help the countries of the region develop and strengthen their role in the global economic system. This strategy plays an important role in the democratic, economic and environmental development of Central Asia.

Unlike Russia or China, the EU has an interest in the integrity and integration of the region. The EU’s integration experience can serve as an example for the region. Therefore, cooperation in this area is also promising.

CONCLUSION: The EU wants to take cooperation with the region to a new level. The region is not against it. Are the EU’s aspirations of strategic importance or temporary until relations with the US or Russia improve? What position will the EU take in the confrontation between China and the US, can it be as neutral as possible? The practical actions of the parties on these issues will determine the prospects for cooperation between the two regions.

The EU’s attempt to take cooperation with the region to a new level indicates the beginning of a new big game in the region. In such conditions, it is important not to repeat the mistakes of our ancestors, to strengthen the process of regional integration, and to skillfully pursue a multi-vector policy. It is important to conduct scientific research on possible processes based on political knowledge. In this regard, it is advisable to form a regional analysis center under the Advisory Council of the Heads of State of Central Asia.

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